

CHROMATOGRAPHIC STUDY OF ANIONIC COMPLEXES. PART VII. SEPARATION OF SOME IONS IN PRESENCE OF CITRATE USING AQUEOUS METHANOL AS SOLVENT

BY ERIC JOHN SINGH AND ARUN K. DEY

An attempt has been made to separate copper(II), cadmium (II), iron(III), nickel(II), and cobalt(II) from binary, ternary, quaternary, and pentanary mixtures by filter paper chromatography, using aqueous methanol as solvent. The effect of adding varying concentrations of citrate as a complexing agent to the solution has been studied.

In general, when two metals are present, the separation is effected up to the addition of nearly one equivalent of the complexing agent (ratio of total metal : citrate = 1:1). With higher concentration of the complexing agent, no sharp separation occurs. When three metals are present, less citrate is required for good separation. When four or more metals are in the mixture, the concentration of citrate varies for good separation.

In previous publications Singh and Dey studied the chromatographic separation of various metal ions in the presence of tartrate as complexing agent, using aqueous ethanol and methanol as solvent (*J. Chromatog.*, 1960, 3, 146; this *Journal*, 1960, 37, 235). We have extended now the work to some mixtures of ions and have attempted to employ complex-formation with citrate for the separation of ions by filter paper strip chromatography, using aqueous methanol as solvent.

EXPERIMENTAL

Solutions of sulphates of copper, nickel, cobalt, iron (III), and cadmium and of sodium citrate were prepared using reagent grade chemicals and standardised as usual. The arrangement for chromatography was that described by Gage *et al.* (*J. Chem. Ed.*, 1950, 27, 159). Series of mixtures were prepared by taking equal concentrations of metals and adding varying quantities of sodium citrate solution, keeping the total volume constant. The equivalents of citrate mentioned in the figures and the description represent the ratio of total concentration of metals (obtained by adding the concentrations of metal in molarity) to the concentration of citrate added. After trials with varying concentrations of aqueous methanol, 50% methanol was found to effect good separation. The mixtures were spotted on Whatman filter paper No. 1 and the chromatograms were run at a constant temperature in a temperature-controlled room at 26°. The time allowed for movement of ions was 90 minutes. In binary, ternary, quaternary, and pentanary mixtures the final concentration of each of the metal ions was 0.05M, 0.042M, 0.031M, and 0.025M respectively. To ascertain the occurrence of good separation of the ions, the R_L and R_T values were determined. The data are recorded in Figs. 1 to 3, showing the variation of the R values with the concentration of citrate employed in some typical cases.

In the following mixtures, a solution containing $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ and H_2S was used for developing in all the cases except in mixtures containing nickel, where dimethylglyoxime was also used.

Separation of Nickel (II) and Copper (II).—The separation of the ions was possible up to 0.4 equiv. of citrate added; with higher concentrations of citrate no satisfactory separation was effected.

Separation of Copper (II) and Iron (III).— $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ was used for developing. The separation of Cu(II) and Fe(III) ions was possible up to one equivalent of citrate added; with higher concentrations of the same no separation was possible. In case of iron (III) tailing occurred up to 0.2 equivalent of citrate added; on increasing the concentrations of the same, tailing was reduced, and finally the R_T value became constant with 0.8 equiv. of citrate added.

Separation of Nickel(II) and Iron (III).—The separation of ions was effected up to 1.3 equiv. of citrate added. When the ratio of metal : concentration of citrate was 1:1.3 to 1:1.5, there was no sharp separation of the ions; with a ratio of 1:1.6 and above, no separation of the ions was possible.

Separation of Cobalt (II) and Iron (III).—The separation of ions was possible up to the addition of 1.5 equiv. of the complexing agent; with higher concentrations of the same, no separation was effected.

Separation of Copper (II) and Cobalt(II).—The separation of ions was effected up to the addition of 0.8 equiv. of the complexing agent; with higher concentrations of the same, no separation was possible. The R values of copper (II) became constant with 0.4 equiv. of the complexing agent added.

Separation of Copper(II) and Cadmium(II).—A good separation of the ions took place with ratios 1:1 to 1:3 equiv. of the complexing agent added. With a ratio of 1:1 or above, cadmium (II) ions did not move, only copper (II) ions moved upwards.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

Separation of Cadmium (II) and Iron (III).—In the beginning no precipitation occurred. When about 3 or more equivalents of citrate were added, a slight precipitate formed after allowing the solution to stand for a long time. The separation of cadmium(II) and iron(III) ions took place up to the addition of 0.8 equiv. of the complexing agent. With ratios of 1:0.9 to 1:2.9, there was no separation of the ions. With a ratio of 1:3 and above, cadmium(II) ions did not move and only iron(III) ions moved upwards.

FIG. 3

FIG. 4

Separation of Copper (II), Cobalt (II), and Iron (III).—The separation of cobalt(II), copper(II), and iron(III) (Fig. 1) was possible up to the addition of 0.76 equiv. of the complexing agent; with higher concentrations of the same, no separation was possible under the experimental conditions. The R_L values of cobalt(II) and iron(III) did not change with small additions of the complexing agent, but on increasing the concentrations of the same, these increased and became constant. The R_L values of cobalt(II) became constant with 0.53 equiv. of the complexing agent added. The R_L values in case of iron(III) became constant with 0.6 equiv. The R_L value of iron(III) became constant with the addition of 0.47 equiv. of citrate.

Separation of Cobalt (II), Cadmium (II), and Copper(II).—Separation of the ions in this case (Fig. 2) was possible up to the addition of 0.39 equiv. of citrate. With higher concentrations of the

same, no separation took place; when one or more equivalents of citrate were added only the separation of cadmium (II) ions was possible from cobalt (II) and copper (II) ions. The R_L values of cobalt (II) and cadmium (II) did not change with small additions of citrate and decreased on increasing the concentrations of the same. The R_L values of copper (II) did not change with small additions of citrate, but increased on increasing the concentrations of the same, and finally showed a tendency to become constant.

Separation of Cobalt (II), Cadmium (II), and Iron (III).—Separation of the ions was effected up to 0.313 equiv. of citrate added; with higher concentration of the same, no separation took place. The R values of cobalt (II) did not change with the addition of citrate. The R_L values of cadmium (II) behaved in a similar manner as in the case of cobalt (II). The R values of iron (III) did not change with small additions of citrate. On increasing the concentrations of the same they tended to increase.

Separation of Cadmium (II), Copper (II), and Iron (III).—Separation of the ions (Fig. 3) was effected up to the addition of 0.39 equiv. of citrate; with higher concentrations of the same, the separation did not occur due to the spreading and overlapping of the zones. The R values of cadmium (II), copper (II), and iron (III) behaved in a similar manner as described earlier.

Separation of Copper (II), Cobalt (II), Iron (III), and Cadmium (II).—The separation of these ions (Fig. 4) was possible up to 0.4 equiv. of citrate added, but with higher concentration of the same, no satisfactory separation took place due to the spreading of the zones. The R_L values of cobalt (II) and cadmium (II) did not change with additions of citrate. The R_L values of copper (II) and iron (III) decreased with small additions of citrate, then continued to decrease as the concentrations of the same were increased, and finally attained constancy with 0.3 equivalents of citrate added.

Separation of Nickel (II), Cobalt (II), and Copper (II).—Only the separation of copper (II) ions was effected up to 0.313 equivalents of the complexing agent added.

Separation of Nickel (II), Cobalt (II), and Iron (III).—The separation of only iron (III) ions was effected from nickel (II) and cobalt (II) ions up to 0.7 equivalent of citrate added. With higher concentrations of the same, no separation took place.

Separation of Nickel (II), Cadmium (II), and Iron (III).—The separation of iron (III) ions only was possible from the mixture of the ions up to the addition of 0.313 equiv. of citrate; with higher concentration, separation did not occur.

Separation of Copper (II), Cobalt (II), Iron (III), and Nickel (II).—The separation of copper (II) and iron (III) ions only was effected up to 0.4 equiv. of citrate added; but on increasing the concentrations of the same, there was no separation.

Separation of Cobalt (II), Cadmium (II), Nickel (II), and Iron (III).—In the separation of these ions only iron (III) could be separated up to the addition of 0.2 equiv. of the complexing agent.

Separation of Nickel (II), Cobalt (II), Cadmium (II), Copper (II), and Iron (III).—Only the separation of copper (II) and iron (III) was effected up to 0.24 equiv. of citrate added. With higher concentrations of the same, no separation took place.